

A novel adenine appended fluorescent chemosensor for phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) and citrate ion sensing in aqueous medium[†]

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Abstract : Adenine appended Schiff base (H_3L) is characterized and shows citrate ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7^{3-}$) and phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) ion selective recognition in green region of visible light. The limit of optical detection (LOD) of sensor for phosphate ion is $4.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ and for citrate ion is $3.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$. The quantum yield (Φ) is increased from 0.0356 to 0.3402 on citrate ion and 0.0356 to 0.418 on phosphate ion binding.

Keywords : Adenine, chemosensor, citrate, phosphate, fluorescence.

Introduction

Anions are obligatory in the living cell¹; the influence of anions on cellular biological processes is controlled via macromolecular receptors, which are protein in nature and involves in many enzymatic transformations, substance transportation, or signal transduction. Therefore, the design and synthesis of ion receptors those can detect biologically relevant anions such as RCOO^- , citrate, P^{V} (phosphates) through optical response is of considerable interest. Citric acid is a tricarboxylic acid ($\text{C}(\text{COOH})(\text{OH})(\text{CH}_2\text{COOH})_2$) and is the key metabolite in the Krebs cycle (citric acid cycle) to virtually every aerobic cell². Decreasing citrate level has been linked to various aspects of kidney dysfunction, such as nephrolithiasis and nephrocalcinosis^{3,4}. Inorganic phosphate (Pi) is the source of energy in biology, $\text{ADP} + \text{Pi} \rightarrow \text{ATP}$ ⁵, and also a prominent water pollutant⁶. The determination of phosphate concentrations in body fluid is necessary; it provides the information of several diseases such as kidney failure⁷. In this respect, considerable efforts have been devoted for the designing of fluorogenic sensor for citrate⁸ and phosphate anions^{9,10}.

Fluorescence spectroscopy is one of the highly sensitive, simple, cheap, high resolution, large signal intensity and commonly used technique to quantify trace amount of

ions¹¹. Though cation chemosensors are relatively well-developed, the search for anion-selective receptors is only recently emerging as a research area of significant importance¹². The interaction (covalent and/or noncovalent) of the analyte with the receptor or binding site is transformed into an electromagnetic signal by the signaling subunit which may be measured by the reporter or transducer. This may be employed for development of chemosensor for fluorogenic identification and estimation of specific ion/molecule¹¹⁻¹³. Recently we have started to design chelating ligands specifically working as turn-on fluorogenic cation sensors^{14,15}. This has encouraged us to search for anion sensors that are really few⁸⁻¹⁰. To the best of our knowledge, very few adenine appended fluorescent anion sensors are reported⁸. Herein, we synthesize a new adenine appended fluorescent chromophore, 2,6-bis-[(7*H*-purin-6-yl)imino)methyl]-4-methylphenol (H_3L) and has been characterized by spectroscopic study which shows high efficiency to investigate the existence of trace amount of phosphate and citrate anions in aquatic environment.

Experimental

Materials :

Analytical reagent grade adenine, 4-methylphenol, hexamethylene tetraamine, formaldehyde were purchased

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

from Sigma and had been used as received. Solvents were purified and dried by literature method¹⁶. The metal salts required for experiments were purchased from Merck, India.

Physical measurements :

Microanalytical data (C, H and N) were collected on Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. ESI mass spectra were recorded from a Water HRMS model XEVO-G2QTOF#YCA351 spectrometer. The measurement was conducted at room temperature. Spectroscopic data were obtained using the following instruments : UV-Vis spectra by Perkin-Elmer UV-Vis spectrophotometer model Lambda 25; FTIR spectra (KBr disk, 4000–400 cm^{-1}) by Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer model RX-1; the ^1H NMR spectra by Bruker (AC) 300 MHz FTNMR spectrometer. Emission was examined by LS 55 Perkin-Elmer spectrofluorimeter at room temperature (298 K) in acetonitrile-water (1 : 9, v/v) solutions under degassed condition. The fluorescence quantum yield of the ligands was determined using anthracene as a reference with known ϕ_{R} of 0.27 in ethanol. The complex and the reference dye were excited at same wavelength, maintaining nearly equal absorbance (~ 0.1), and the emission spectra were recorded. The area of the emission spectrum was integrated using the software available in the instrument and the quantum yield is calculated according to the following equation :

$$\frac{\phi_{\text{S}}}{\phi_{\text{R}}} = \left[\frac{A_{\text{S}}}{A_{\text{R}}} \right] \times \left[\frac{(\text{Abs})_{\text{R}}}{(\text{Abs})_{\text{S}}} \right] \times \left[\frac{\eta_{\text{S}}^2}{\eta_{\text{R}}^2} \right]$$

Here, ϕ_{S} and ϕ_{R} are the fluorescence quantum yield of the sample and reference, respectively. A_{S} and A_{R} are the area under the fluorescence spectra of the sample and the reference, respectively, $(\text{Abs})_{\text{S}}$ and $(\text{Abs})_{\text{R}}$ are the respective optical densities of the sample and the reference solution at the wavelength of excitation, and η_{S} and η_{R} are the values of refractive index for the respective solvent used for the sample and reference.

Synthesis of 2,6-bis-[(7H-purin-6-yl)imino)methyl]-4-methylphenol (H_3L) :

Adenine (1.35 g, 9.99 mmol) in dry methanol (10 mL) was added in drops to 2-hydroxy-5-methylisophthalaldehyde (0.82 g, 4.995 mmol), in the same solvent (10 mL) and refluxed under dry nitrogen for 2 h. Solution

turned to yellow and was slowly allowed to cool and evaporate in air. Yellow crystals were deposited and filtered and dried. Yield : 1.89 g (95%); m.p. 220 ± 2 °C. Anal. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}$ Calcd : C, 57.28; H, 3.54; N, 35.16. Found : C, 57.39; H, 3.47; N, 35.10%. Molecular ion peak (m/z), 399.07, $(\text{M}+\text{H})^+$. Calcd. mol. wt : 391.4 (Supplementary Material, Fig. S1); FT-IR (KBr, ν , cm^{-1}) $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1649; $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$, 1351; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$, 1547; $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$, 3443 (Supplementary Material, Fig. S2). The ^1H NMR spectrum of H_3L (300 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) demonstrates singlet signal at 11.47 ppm corresponds to $\delta(\text{OH})$ and $\delta(\text{NH})$; imine-H ($\text{CH}=\text{N}$) and pyrimidyl 10,10'-H appear at δ 10.24 ppm; 3,5-H is observed at 7.76 ppm and imidazolyl 15,15'-H emerge at 7.28 ppm (Supplementary Material, Fig. S3).

Adduct of H_3L with PO_4^{3-} and citrate :

A mixture of pale yellow colored crystalline H_3L (0.100 g, 0.25 mmol) and Na_3PO_4 (0.041 g, 0.25 mmol) or $\text{Na}_3\text{citrate}$ (anhydrous) (0.65 g, 0.25 mmol) in acetonitrile-water (1 : 9, v/v) in presence of few drops of dilute HCl was allowed to evaporate slowly in air. Yellow-products were recrystallised from acetonitrile solution by slow evaporation. Yield : Phosphate-adduct 0.09 g (72%); Citrate-adduct (0.100 g, 68%). Microanalytical data of the adduct have been used to establish the composition; H_6L -phosphate, Anal. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_5\text{P}$; Calcd : C, 47.97; H, 3.45; N, 28.22. Found : C, 47.76; H, 3.60; N, 28.26%. H_6L -Citrate, $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_8$ Calcd : C, 50.85; H, 3.76; N, 23.72. Found : C, 51.62; H, 3.82; N, 23.86%. Mass ion peak (m/z) of $[\text{H}_6\text{L}\text{-phosphate}]$ appears at 515.12 which corresponds to $(\text{H}_6\text{L}\text{-phosphate}+\text{Na})$, calcd. mass 519 and $[\text{H}_6\text{L}\text{-citrate}]$ adduct refers to m/z , 599.13 of $(\text{H}_6\text{L}+\text{H}_3\text{citrate}+\text{H})$ (Supplementary Material, Figs. S4, S5); FT-IR (KBr, ν , cm^{-1}) $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1576; $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$, 1335; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$, 1455; $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$, 3030; $\nu(\text{P}-\text{O})$, 1060, 910, 840 cm^{-1} for H_3L -phosphate (Supplementary Material, Fig. S6) and $\nu(\text{citrate})$, 1920, 1780, 1680; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1525; $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$, 1315; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$, 1405; $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$, 3550 cm^{-1} for H_6L -citrate (Supplementary Material, Fig. S7). ^1H NMR spectra of these adducts are not very informative because of quick turbidity in CDCl_3 and $\text{DMSO}-d_6$.

Fluorescence sensing of metal ions and titration :

For UV-Vis and fluorescence titration, stock solution of H_3L was prepared (6.6 μM) in acetonitrile-water (1 : 9,

v/v) (at 25 °C) using tris HCl buffered solution. The metal ion solutions were prepared using their chlorides/nitrates in same solvent and buffer in order of 1×10^{-4} M. The spectra of these solutions were recorded in UV-Vis and fluorescence spectrometer.

Quantification of stoichiometry by Job's plot in fluorescence spectroscopy and LOD measurement :

From stock solution of H_3L and anion we prepared 6.6 μ M concentration of both solution in acetonitrile-water (1 : 9, v/v) at 25 °C and emission spectra recorded at different citrate and phosphate ion and ligand ratio but in equal volume. A plot of emission intensity vs mole fraction of ion at 550 nm is performed.

The limit of optical detection (LOD) is calculated based on the fluorescence titration by the equation : $LOD = K \times Sd1/S$ where $K = 2$ or 3 (we take 3 in this case); $Sd1$ is the standard deviation of the blank solution; S is the slope of the calibration curve.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation of H_3L :

The reaction of 2-hydroxy-5-methylisophthalaldehyde with adenine in methanol solution under refluxing condition has isolated bright yellow colored crystalline 2,6-bis-[(7H-purin-6-yl)imino)methyl]-4-methylphenol (H_3L). It has been purified by repeated crystallization from acetonitrile. The composition has been supported by microanalytical and mass spectral data (Supplementary Material, Fig. S1). Upon slow evaporation of acetonitrile-methanol solution (1 : 1, v/v) of Na_3PO_4 and H_3L (1 : 1, mole ratio) or sodium citrate (Na_3 citrate) and H_3L (1 : 1, mole ratio) in presence of few drops of dilute HCl at room temperature has separated yellow-green crystalline product in 72% and 68% respectively. The composition of

adduct has been supported by microanalytical and mass spectral data (Supplementary Material, Figs. S4, S5).

In FTIR spectrum H_3L shows $\nu(C=N)$ at 1649 cm^{-1} along with other functional groups in predictable frequency position. The $\nu(NH)$ and $\nu(OH)$ appear at 3070 cm^{-1} and 3457 cm^{-1} . The 1H NMR spectral data of H_3L shows signals for imine -CH and phenolic-OH proton at 10.2 ppm to 11.47 ppm respectively. The adenine and aromatic protons show signal at 7.2–7.7 ppm (Supplementary Material, Fig. S3). FT-IR spectra are informative to the adducts¹⁷; appearance of transmission at 1060, 910 and 840 cm^{-1} refer to phosphate vibrations in H_6L -phosphate and 1920, 1780, 1680 cm^{-1} correspond to $\nu(\text{citrate})$ in H_6L -citrate; other vibrations of $\nu(C=N)$, $\nu(C-O)$ etc. have been shifted to lower frequency which may be due to strong interaction with H_3L (Supplementary Material, Figs. S6, S7).

The absorption spectrum of H_3L in acetonitrile shows two well defined intense absorption bands at region 348 nm and 440 nm and is the characteristic of intramolecular charge transfer transitions. In spectrophotometric titration of 2.5 μ M acetonitrile-water (1 : 9, v/v) solution of H_3L on gradual addition of PO_4^{3-} ion shows red shifting (348 nm to 441 nm, Fig. 1(a)) with sudden raise of intensity and two clear isobestic points at 309 nm and 375 nm respectively and for citrate these are (346 nm to 438 nm) and isobestic points are at 312 nm and 378 nm respectively (Fig. 1(b)).

Fluorescence sensing and titration :

The fluorescence spectrum of H_3L with several anions (F^- , SCN^- , I^- , CH_3COO^- , PF_6^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , citrate³⁻, PO_4^{3-} , HPO_4^{2-} , $H_2PO_4^-$, $P_2O_7^{4-}$) using their sodium or potassium salts in acetonitrile-water (1 : 9, v/v) (HEPES buffer, pH = 7.4) solution have been examined on exci-

Fig. 1. Spectral changes upon addition of aqueous solution of (a) Na_3PO_4 and (b) $\text{Na}_3\text{citrate}$ in acetonitrile solution of H_3L in dilute HCl.

tation at 345 nm (citrate)/420 nm (phosphate) (Fig. 2) and the turn-on emission is observed in presence of PO_4^{3-} and citrate (separately added) at room temperature (25 °C). In the presence of PO_4^{3-} or citrate the emission maxima

Fig. 2. Relative metal ions and anions sensitivity of H_3L .

has been shifted to 550 nm for both the ions which implies the chemical interaction between H_3L and anions. On increasing the concentration of PO_4^{3-} or citrate the fluorescence intensity increases and becomes saturated on adding ~ 1.1 equivalent of ions (Fig. 3).

The cations viz. K^+ , Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{2+} etc. do not affect the fluorescence property of H_3L . This specific selectivity for anions has been established by the single and

triple anion studies by taking 5 equivalent citrate and phosphate ions and other competing anions in $2.5 \mu\text{M}$ ligand solution (Fig. 4). The rapid fluorescence turn-on response in titration of Schiff base has been performed by gradual increasing the concentration of phosphate and citrate anions (0–145 μM and 0–160 μM) in acetonitrile-water (1 : 9, v/v) solution of H_3L . A linear plot of the emission intensity vs concentration of anion (PO_4^{3-} or citrate^{3-}) is obtained from which respective unknown anion concentration of a sample may be easily measured. The confirmation of 1 : 1 stoichiometric complexation H_3L -anion (citrate and PO_4^{3-}) is performed by Jobs plot in emission spectroscopy (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S8) and mass spectroscopy with characteristic peaks (Supplementary Materials, Figs. S4, S5).

The apparent binding constant measured adopting Benesi-Hildebrand equation : $(F_{\text{max}} - F_0)/(F_x - F_0) = 1 + (1/K)(1/[M])^n$, where F_{max} , F_0 and F_x are respective fluorescence intensities of H_3L in the presence of ion at saturation, free sensor, and any intermediate ion concentration. The binding constant of H_3L - PO_4^{3-} and H_3L -citrate are $3.05 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ and $9.8 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$, respectively. Limit of optical detection (LOD) are $4.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ (PO_4^{3-}) and $3.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ (citrate) (Fig. 5).

Upon excitation of H_3L in methanol solution at 346 nm emits at 460 nm and the quantum yield (Φ) is 0.0356. Citrate and phosphate adduct of sensor (H_3L) absorbs at 438 nm and hence excitation is carried out at this wavelength; they also emit at 550 nm (Fig. 6) with high quan-

Fig. 3. Fluorometric titration of H₃L with the addition of (a) PO₄³⁻ and (b) citrate³⁻ in acetonitrile-aqueous medium (1 : 9, v/v).

Fig. 4. Change of emission intensity at 500 nm for single and triple anion sensitivity of H₃L.

Fig. 5. The linear dynamic response of H₃L upon addition of (a) Na₃PO₄ and (b) Na₃citrate and the determination of the detection limit (LOD) for citrate.

Fig. 6. Life profile of excited state of H₃L and its adducts.

tum yields at 0.3402 and 0.4180. The stability of excited state of sensor and two adducts are significantly different; life time (τ) of H₃L is 0.2655 ns while citrate-adduct shows 1.96 ns and phosphate-adduct shows longest life time data, 3.671 ns. Nonradiative rate constants ($k_{nr} \times 10^{-9}$) are longer (9.673 (H₃L), 0.2742 (citrate-adduct), 0.0542 (phosphate-adduct)) than radiative rate data ($k_r \times 10^{-9}$) (0.6730 (H₃L), 0.0075 (citrate-adduct), 0.0064 (phosphate-adduct)).

Conclusion

Adenine appended Schiff base, 2,6-bis-[(7*H*-purin-6-yl)imino)methyl]-4-methylphenol serves as fluorogenic sensor to phosphate (PO₄³⁻) and citrate in presence of anions such as F⁻, SCN⁻, I⁻, CH₃COO⁻, PF₆³⁻, SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, citrate, PO₄³⁻, HPO₄²⁻, H₂PO₄⁻, P₂O₇⁴⁻ and cations such as K⁺, Ba²⁺, Mg²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺, Co²⁺, Pb²⁺, Ni²⁺, Fe²⁺. The sensor has been characterized by spectroscopic data. The adduct formation of the sensor with phosphate or citrate follows 1 : 1 mole ratio which have been examined by Jobs method of continuous variation (binding constants are $K_a = 3.05 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ (H₆L-PO₄³⁻) and $9.8 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ (H₆L-citrate)) and also by mass spectral data. Limit of detection calculated using Benesi-Hildebrand equation are 4.1×10^{-4} (phosphate) and 3.8×10^{-5} (citrate).

Supporting materials

All spectroscopic figures are given in Supplementary Materials Section (Figs. S1- S10).

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